

Master Thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

A Computational Model for Spectral Modulation and Speech Perception Performance of Cochlear Implant Users

Franklin Y. Alvarez

Supervisor: Waldo Nogueira

Co-Supervisor: Jordi Pons

August 2019

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Dedication

I would like to dedicate this work to my mother and my wife, the two girls that really gave me their support to do this Master.

Gracias Ma, por insistir en una carrera en la academia.

Gracias Andre, por mantenerme vivo mientras trabajaba y estudiaba, y por acompañarme hasta Hanover. Este título no es sólo mío, es nuestro.

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Also, I would like to acknowledge Daniel's research work at the APG. The peripheral auditory model presented in this research is mostly based on it.

Abstract

In the development of new technologies for cochlear implants (CIs), there are many evaluation procedures that have to be done until it is implemented on hearing devices. The majority of such procedures consist of asking implanted volunteers to perform auditory tasks, but collecting the required data is time demanding.

In this work, a computational model is presented to simulate two of the many tasks typically used to evaluate CI users performance: speech reception threshold (SRT), and spectral modulation threshold (SMT). The model uses a cochlear implant sound coding strategy, a peripheral auditory model to obtain the spike activity from auditory nerves and an adapter to extract the internal representation (IR). As back-end, the simulation framework for auditory discrimination experiments (FADE) is implemented. The performance of three different CI sound coding strategies were compared, one with sequential stimulation and the other two with simultaneous stimulation with two and three channels respectively. Also, the impact of nerve fiber degeneration and number of functional fibers was studied.

The model successfully performed SRT and SMT experiments resembling CI users. The CI sound coding strategy with triplet simultaneous stimulation performed the best in SRT experiments contrary to the empirical data, but the cause is discussed to be a mismatch in the overall firing rate between sound coding strategies. In SMT experiments the results were quite similar among the strategies. With worse nerve conditions, SRT performance decreased significantly while SMT performance barely changed. It is discussed that the model may be relying in the overall firing rate instead of the spectral shape to identify spectral ripple stimuli.

Finally, It is discussed how different features affects the performance of the model, and whether is necessary to implement a different back-end to avoid modeling central auditory processes.

Keywords: cochlear implants; FADE; CI sound coding strategy; computational modeling; speech reception threshold; spectral modulation threshold.

Chapter 1

Introduction

The cochlear implant (CI) is an implantable medical device that can restore sense of hearing in people suffering from profound hearing loss. Nevertheless, there is a big gap between normal hearing (NH) and implanted people in many auditory tasks, especially in speech-in-noise recognition. This is the reason why many researchers are dedicated to improve the performance of these auditory devices. In this context, the Auditory Prosthetic Group (APG) [1] is running research on individual models of the cochlea for CI users (IndiMoCI), understanding how CI users perceive music (MuSIProCI), studying binaural signal processing for CIs (BINOM), and researching on electroacoustic stimulation when combining hearing aid devices and CIs (EAS-Masking).

This research is supported by the APG, and relies specially on the IndiMoCI research project. The goal is to develop a computational model that can be individualized to each CI user for clinical uses [2], and also work as a tool to develop better front-end algorithms for CI devices.

The University of Oldenburg is developing a simulation framework for auditory discrimination experiments (FADE) which has been used to predict speech recognition performance of hearing impaired people [3]. FADE uses a universal set of parameters to predict the psychoacoustic performance, such as tone-in-noise detection and speech-in-noise recognition [4]. Such a framework could be used, along with

an auditory model, to develop a computational tool capable of predicting CI users performance in both tasks.

Taking this assumptions into account, the motivation, objectives, and structure of this work is presented in the next sections.

1.1 Motivation

The usefulness of a computational tool that incorporates the advances in modeling the human auditory system and a framework to predict psychoacoustic and speech recognition tasks can be found in many areas, such as:

- Development of new front-end coding strategies and algorithms for CI devices using the computational model as a preliminary evaluation tool.
- Clinical planning, before and after implantation, by individualizing physiological parameters in the computational model such as cochlear dimensions or electrode position.
- Support in research and experiments related to the nerve condition of the peripheral auditory system. The nerve degeneration cannot be directly measured and it is a possible cause of the high performance variability among CI users.

1.2 Objective

The aim of this work is subdivided in four objectives. The first objective is to use FADE as the back-end prediction tool and the IndiMoCI cochlear model as the electrode-nerve interface, to build a computational model that performs the following tasks:

1. Generate a training and a testing stimuli corpus in *.wav* format
2. Process the generated corpus using a CI sound coding strategy

3. Extract features from the processed corpus using the electrode-nerve interface and a feature extraction algorithm
4. Train a hidden Markov model (HMM) using the features extracted from the training corpus
5. Recognize the stimuli using the features from the testing corpus and the trained HMM.
6. Evaluate the performance of the HMM.

The second objective is to use the computational model to perform two different experiments:

- Speech-in-noise perception
- Spectral modulation detection

The third goal is to compare the computational model's performance using three different CI sound coding strategy (sequential, paired, and triplet) with empirical data obtained by Langner et al. [5]

Finally, the fourth objective is to elaborate a preliminary parametric study of the neural health parameters modeled in the electrode-nerve interface.

1.3 Structure of the report

The rest of this work is organized in five further chapters. Chapter 2 is a review of the most important concepts in the topic of CIs. Chapter 3 is a review of the state-of-the-art in modeling our auditory system. Chapter 4 is a description of the proposed computational model and how it performs the experiments. Chapter 5 presents the results. Chapter 6 is the final discussion and conclusion of this work.

Because this thesis is part of the sound and music computing (SMC) master, it is considered that the reader has some basic knowledge in audio signal processing (ASP), programming and machine learning.

Chapter 2

A review of the auditory system and cochlear implants

This chapter reviews of concepts related to the human auditory system and CIs. It is focused on the health of the auditory nerves, CI sound coding strategies, and auditory performance tests.

2.1 Human auditory system

The principal organ of the human auditory system is the ear, which is responsible of hearing and balance. Figure 1 shows the whole structure of the ear. It is divided in three sections with specific functions. The outer ear, composed by the auricle (also known as pinna) and the external auditory canal, is responsible for transmitting the sound wave into the tympanic cavity, amplifying frequencies around 4 kHz. The shape of the auricle plays also an important role in sound localization [6] [7]. The middle ear is composed by the tympanic cavity and the ossicles: malleus, incus, and the stapes. The ossicles mechanically connect the tympanic membrane to the oval window at the base of the cochlea. Their function is to match the mechanical impedance between the outer ear and the inner ear.

The inner ear consist of the bony labyrinth that contains the cochlea, a bone chamber

Figure 1: The ear and its parts [6]. The outer ear consists of the auricle and the external auditory canal. The middle ear is located in the tympanic cavity and consists of the ossicles: malleus, incus and stapes. The inner ear consists of the bony labyrinth containing the cochlea.

where the sound wave propagates and stimulates the fibers of the auditory nerve. Figure 2 shows that the cochlea is snail shaped (*A*) and its sensitivity to frequencies is tonotopically arranged along the basilar membrane, from high frequencies towards the base (around 20 kHz) to low frequencies towards the apex (around 200 Hz) (*B*). A transverse view reveals three ducts called scalas separated by the basilar and vestibuli membranes (*C*). The scala tympani and the scala vestibuli are filled with perilymph fluid while the scala media is filled with endolymph fluid. Inside the scala media is the organ of corti delimited by the tectorial membrane and the basilar membrane (*D*) [7] [8].

In the organ of corti the hair cells are located, classified as inner hair cells (IHCs) and outer hair cells (OHCs). When a sound wave reaches the cochlea, the perilymph fluid inside the scala tympani vibrates. These vibrations will generate a vertical oscillation of the basilar membrane, and consequently, an horizontal oscillation of the tectorial membrane. This is represented in Figure 3. The movement of the tectorial membrane causes a deflection in the stereocilia filaments located at the top of the IHCs, the deflection will lead to electrical current impulses that reach the auditory nerve fibers and produce an action potential, also called a spike. The spikes travel through the nerve fibers into the spiral ganglion, and then, through the

Figure 2: Anatomy of the cochlea [8]. **(A)**: The snail shaped bony body of the cochlea. **(B)**: The cochlea responds to the sound waves tonotopically from high frequencies in the base to low frequencies in the apex. **(C)**: The scalas inside the bony walls of the cochlea: scala tympani, scala media and scala vestibuli. **(D)**: The organ of corti located in the scala media between the basilar and the tectorial membrane.

cochlear nerve into the brainstem [7] [8] [9].

Figure 3: Transverse cut of the organ of corti [9]. The vertical vibration of the perilymph inside the scala tympani is transmitted to the basilar membrane. The tectorial membrane oscillates horizontally deflecting the stereocilia of the inner hair cells. This will lead to an electrical stimulation in auditory nerve fiber attached to it.

The function of the OHCs is not completely understood, but it is suggested that

they are part of the efferent nervous system in the cochlea controlling mechanical properties of the organ of corti. OHCs are responsible of the fine tuning and the amplification of certain frequencies in the basilar membrane [7] [10].

From the spikes traveling through the human auditory system the brain is capable of coding sounds, and there are some hypothesis on how this coding relates to pitch and loudness perception. According to Moore (2003) [7], pitch and loudness are not coded completely separated, and they depend mainly on three conditions: the neural firing rate, the phase locking, and the across place coincidence detectors.

Heeger (2006), defines the firing rate as the amount of spikes generated in a time interval [11]. Because there are hair cells that start firing at different sound thresholds, loudness perception depends on how many nerve fibers are spiking in a time frame around 7 ms [12]. Phase locking is defined as the synchronization between the spikes generation in the nerve fibers and the phase of the sound wave [11]. The across place coincidence detectors are neurons capable of detecting minimum phase changes when two fibers with slightly different location fire synchronously [7].

The coding of pure tone signals is shown in Figure 4. It is a representation of the spike train of two auditory nerve fibers, one located near the apex (*position 1*), and the other near the base (*position 2*) of the cochlea. The acoustic signal is representing from the top to the bottom column: a quiet low frequency tone, a loud low frequency tone, a quiet high frequency tone, and a loud high frequency tone.

When it comes to complex sounds, the peripheral auditory system will behave as a bank of band-pass filters, and the timbre perception will mostly depend on the relative loudness perceived among those filters. It is known that there are up to 39 independent auditory filters available to code complex sounds, but only 28 of them are located in the frequency range of speech signals [7].

2.2 Neural health in hearing impaired people

Sensorineural hearing loss is mainly caused by damaged hair cells. The reason could vary from genetics, disease, age, continuous exposure to loud sounds, or a combina-

Pitch and loudness

Figure 4: Firing rate and phase locking theory representation in two auditory nerves located in the apex (*position 1*) and in the base (*position 2*) of the cochlea [11]. Phase locking is observable because the nerve fires only around the positive part of the acoustic signal carrying information about the pitch. The firing rate increases with the amplitude of the acoustic signal as well.

tion of them. If the IHCs are not capable of inducing spikes in the auditory nerves, the physiological consequence is that the fibers connected to them will degenerate towards the spiral ganglion. This degeneration can vary among different persons and cannot be measured directly without removing the cochlea. It can only be indirectly guessed using duration of deafness as a predictor [13] [14]. It is thought that the high variability in auditory performances among CI users is caused by their individual neural health [15].

An indirect way to measure neural health, only in already implanted subjects, is proposed by Ramekers et al. (2014) [13]. Some CI devices are equipped with a reverse telemetry interface that allows the measurement of electrical signals using the same electrodes that stimulates the auditory nerves. With this feature, the electrically evoked compound action potential (eCAP) is measured. The eCAP is defined as the synchronous response of a population of electrically stimulated auditory nerve fibers

and its value is proportional to the amplitude difference between the first valley (N_1) and the first peak (P_2) of the measured signal [16]. Figure 5 shows the eCAP recorded from normal hearing guinea pigs (*A*) and after six weeks of being deafened (*B*). The response is plotted at different amplitudes of stimulus current. Note that the eCAP is increasing with the amplitude and is also bigger when the nerve fibers are healthy.

Figure 5: eCAP recorded in guinea pigs with normal hearing (*A*) and after six weeks of being deafened (*B*) [13]. The right labels represent the different stimulus current levels.

2.3 Cochlear implants

Among the different implantable auditory devices, the most common implant is the CI. It consists of a microphone, a sound processor, a transmitter located right behind the patient's ear, a receiver located between the skull and skin aligned with the transmitter, and an electrode array inserted in the scala tympani of the patient's cochlea. The electrode array normally consists of up to 22 electrodes depending on the manufacturer. Figure 6 shows the CI parts. CIs are implanted mostly on patients with severe hearing loss, but with healthy auditory nerves or spiral ganglion.

Its function is to bypass the non existing IHCs and to generate electrical pulses with the electrode array to try to evoke the spike activity of a normal hearing person [7] [8] [9] [17].

Figure 6: Parts of the cochlear implant [8]. The microphone, audio processor, and transmitter are the external parts. The receiver is implanted in the skull of the patient and the electrode array inside the scala tympani of the cochlea.

With up to 22 electrodes the implant is trying to substitute around 3400 IHCs and stimulate 30000 to 40000 auditory nerve fibers [9]. It is evident that there is a big loss on resolution to code loudness and pitch as compared to NH listeners. The sound coding strategies, which are the bridge between acoustic sound waves and electrical stimulation patterns, try to compensate this loss.

2.4 Cochlear implant sound coding strategies

Sound coding strategies for CIs have been evolving since first implants were made. By the year 1993, Wilson et al. published a study comparing two different strategies: compressed analog (CA), and continuous interleaved sampling (CIS). The CIS strategy was the innovation at that moment and performed way better than the CA strategy [18]. CIS strategy generates biphasic pulses of current sequentially in an

apical to basal order, as shown in Figure 7. A biphasic pulse of current consists of a cathodic (negatively charged) and an anodic (positively charged) phase that balance the stimulation charges, and avoid nerve tissue damage [19]. The principal characteristics of these biphasic pulses are: pulse width d (typically around $20 \mu\text{s}$), pulse *rate* (typically between 500 and 2000 pps), and amplitude which is below the range of 1 mA when coding loud sounds. These values are adjusted in a procedure called "mapping" to the individual needs of CI users.

Figure 7: Electrodiagram of the CIS sound coding strategy with four electrodes [18]. The x-axis is time and y-axis is the current amplitude of the stimulus. d is the duration of one phase of the biphasic pulses and the *rate* is the pulses occurrence per second. Pulses are generated in a sequential order from the most apical electrode (4) to the most basal (1).

To code the sounds with CIS strategy, the signal captured by the microphone is processed by a front-end algorithm that consists mainly in compression. Then, it is band-pass filtered into as many channels as electrodes are implanted. These channels are tonotopically arranged along the array to preserve the frequency distribution in the basilar membrane as good as possible. The amplitude of the pulses in an electrode is related to the envelope signal of the corresponding filter, and mapped in a nonlinear way depending on the minimum and maximum values obtained in the mapping procedure [9] [20]. Figure 8 shows a block diagram of the CIS sound coding strategy.

Biphasic current pulses in the CIS strategy occur in a monopolar stimulation mode where the returning electrode is located considerably far away from the cochlea in the temporally muscle. The electrical potential spread along the basilar membrane has a peak in its closest point to the electrode and diminishes gradually with distance. Based on CIS, some other strategies use "flanks", which are simultaneously

Figure 8: Continuous interleaved sampling (CIS) sound coding strategy [9]. The audio signal is captured by a microphone, processed with a pre-emphasis (*pre-emp*) and an automatic gain control (*AGC*) algorithm, band-pass filtered into M channels with center frequencies along the speech range (*BPF1* to *BPFM*), the envelope is detected for every channel and finally mapped to generate the biphasic pulses.

stimulated phase shifted biphasic pulses. "Flanks" sharpen the electrical potential spread in the basilar membrane obtaining a better selectivity of the nerve fibers that are being stimulated. This is called focused stimulation, and the variant described is "tripolar" stimulation [21].

The F120 coding strategy, also based on CIS, uses current steering to generate up to 120 virtual channels with only 16 electrodes. Current steering consists of generating biphasic pulses simultaneously in two adjacent electrodes with the same phase but different amplitude. This methodology focuses the electrical potential peak somewhere between the closest points of each electrode to the basilar membrane [5] [9] [20]. Figure 9 shows the monopolar, tripolar and current steering stimulation effects along the cochlea.

The relation in amplitude between the electrode pair in current steering is given by α , with $\alpha = 1$ being a pulse generated only at the most apical electrode, and $\alpha = 0.5$ being both pulses stimulating with the same amplitude. Figure 10 shows a temporal representation of the 120 virtual channels created in current steering strategies [5].

With the F120 strategy, the signal is band-pass filtered to $M - 1$ current steering channels, being M the number of electrodes implanted equal to 16. As with CIS strategy, an envelope detection is implemented to control the amplitude of the pulses, while in parallel, a spectral peak locator detects the prominent frequency inside the

Figure 9: Representation of three different stimulation modes [5]. **Monopolar:** The voltage spread in the scala tympani (*cochlear place*) is bell shaped with the peak located in the corresponding position to the stimulating electrode 2. **Current steering:** A current steering channel, formed with the adjacent electrodes 1 and 2, locates the peak of the potential spread between them. **Tripolar:** The electrodes 1 and 3 are phase shifted with respect to the stimulating electrode 2, sharpening the electrical potential even more to the closest point between the stimulating electrode 2 and the basilar membrane.

Figure 10: Representation of the HINT sentence "A boy fell from a window" in the 120 virtual channels generated by the F120 sound coding strategy [20]. The 16 electrodes are enumerated in the left y-axis.

channel's frequency band to adjust the value of α . The carrier synthesis generates a train of pulses at the detected frequency to enhance temporal clues for pitch perception. The spectral peak locator may implement a psychoacoustic model of our sound perception, similar to the one used in the MP3 compression [22]. Figure 11 shows a block diagram of the F120 sound coding strategy.

Figure 11: F120 sound coding strategy block diagram [22]. It starts with an analog to digital (A/D) conversion of the signal and a front-end algorithm that mainly performs compression. A fast Fourier transform (FFT) of length L is applied and the signal is divided in N frequency bands, with $N = M - 1$. Each band is associated to a current steering channel, where an envelope detection and a spectral peak locator algorithm is performed. Depending on the frequency of the peak, the pulses of the electrode pair (E_m, E_{m-1}) are weighted and a pulse train with the detected peak frequency is generated by a carrier synthesis algorithm. Finally, the mapping adjusts the amplitude of the pulses to individual comfort values for each CI user.

Figure 12 shows three different pulses tables, which are pattern of stimulus delivered in one cycle. These pulse tables are derived from the F120: sequential (F120-S), paired (F120-P), and triplet (F120-T). F120-S and F120-P are used commercially, while F120-T is only used for research purpose. F120-P and F120-T simultaneously activate two and three current steering channels respectively. The electrical field summation generated by the simultaneously activated channels helps to decrease the power consumption of the device because less current is needed to obtain the same loudness perception, but it also affects negatively frequency resolution because many nerve fibers in different positions are being stimulated simultaneously [5]. To keep temporal resolution constant among the different pulse tables, a zero current phase, or "rest", between consecutive pulses is applied in F120-P and F120-T pulse tables.

Figure 12: Representation in time (x-axis) of the electrode activity in the array (E1 to E16) for the three F120 pulse tables [5]. From left to right, columns are sequential (F120-S), paired (F120-P), and triplet (F120-T) pulse tables. Notice that in the F120-S table the pair of pulses are generated immediately one after another while in the F120-P two, and in the F120-T three, pairs of pulses are simultaneously generated with a time gap between the next one. These gaps are implemented to preserve the temporal resolution among them.

2.5 Speech reception and spectral modulation threshold

Speech performance in noise is a measure to evaluate hearing performance of CI users. The *Oldenburg Satztest* (OLSA) by Wagener et al. (1999) [23] is a matrix sentence test that consists of 50 words of different categories: name, verb, number, adjective, and noun. Each category containing 10 samples. The sentence will be constructed with one word from each category following the previously mentioned order. There is a total of 100 thousand possible sentence combinations. In a closed test procedure, a sentence is presented to the participant mixed with noise at an spe-

cific signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). The participant is asked to repeat the sentence with previous knowledge of the 50 possible words. Wagener et al. used a psychometric function to describe the performance of the participants and defined the speech reception threshold (SRT) as the SNR at which 50% of the words are correctly guessed [23]. Table 1 presents an example of a matrix sentence in English, and Figure 13 shows the psychometric function used to describe the participant performance, and measure its SRT.

Table 1: Matrix test in English (US) [24]

Name	Verb	Number	Adjective	Noun
Peter	got	three	large	desks
Kathy	sees	nine	small	chairs
Lucy	brought	seven	old	tables
Alan	gives	eight	dark	toys
Rachel	sold	four	heavy	spoons
William	prefers	nineteen	green	windows
Steven	has	two	cheap	sofas
Thomas	kept	fifteen	pretty	rings
Doris	ordered	twelve	red	flowers
Nina	wants	sixty	white	houses

A NH participant is expected to obtain a SRT between -9 dB SNR (no hearing loss) and 7 dB SNR (severe hearing loss) according to the empirical data used by Kollmeier et al. (2016) [3]. Performance of a CI users varies from one to another. Jürgens et al. (2018) obtained SRT measurements between 0 and 7 dB SNR in a group of 14 participants [25].

Another indicative test of individual hearing performance is described by Litvak et al. (2007) [26]. It consists of measuring the smallest detectable spectral contrast in spectral rippled noise. The spectral shape of spectral rippled noise is sinusoidal, as shown in Figure 14, and it is generated using Equation 2.1, where $|F(f)|$ is the magnitude at the frequency bin f , Ct is the spectral contrast, RPO the ripple-per-

Figure 13: Speech-in-noise performance of a participant using the Oldenburg sentence test (OLSA) [23]. "List specific" results are obtained using a subset of 20 sentences where every word appears two times. "Test specific" result is the overall performance. The speech reception threshold (SRT) is obtained when the psychometric function crosses the 50% score.

octave, and θ_0 is the ripple starting phase in the spectrum. The signal is also hard filtered at the edges, and the spectrum phase is randomized when performing the inverse FFT.

$$|F(f)| = \begin{cases} 10^{\frac{Ct}{2} \sin(2\pi(\log_2(f/350))RPO+\theta_0)/20} & 350 < f < 5600 \\ 0 & otherwise \end{cases} \quad (2.1)$$

To obtain the spectral modulation threshold (SMT), a force choice procedure is implemented where three samples are presented: two reference samples with $Ct = 0$, and one target sample with a variable contrast Ct_{target} . The first sample is always a reference noise, hence the participant has to indicate if the target sample is presented in the second or third position. When the participant correctly answer three consecutive times, the contrast Ct_{target} is decreased, but it takes only one wrong answer to reverse the Ct_{target} to its previous value. The SMT is the average

Figure 14: Spectral shape of a spectral ripple noise stimulus with a $RPO = 0.5$ and a contrast depth $Ct = 7dB$. The spectrum is hard filtered at the edges values of 350 Hz and 5600 Hz.

Ct_{target} value where the last even number of reversals occurred, excluding the first three. This adaptative procedure is described by Levitt, and has an equilibrium point of 79.4% correct answers [26] [27].

Litvak et al. compared the performance of CI users in vowel and consonant recognition tests with the SMT. The RPO values of 0.25 and 0.5 were used in those experiments arguing that this modulation frequencies better represents the spectral modulations found in speech [26]. Figure 15 shows a relation between the SMT in dB and the percentage of correctly detected vowels and consonants. The SMT measured among the CI participants ranged between 2 dB (very good performer) and 20 dB (very bad performer).

Also, Langner et al. (2017) measured the SMT and the speech intelligibility in CI users using the F120-S pulse table, and then switching to F120-P or F120-T to determine how much the performance decreased [5]. The results obtained by Langner et al. are shown in Figure 16, suggesting that F120-T worsen significantly the performance, while F120-P performed similarly to the F120-S. Because the trend

Figure 15: Correlation between vowel recognition (left chart) and consonant recognition (right chart) with the spectral modulation threshold (SMT) [26]. The data is obtained from CI users and normal hearing (NH) participants using vocoders at different settings to emulate the spectral resolution loss found in implanted people. The best fit is a regression of the data collected from NH participants (dashed line) and from the CI users (continuous line). Notice that the x-axis is logarithmic, indicating that the relation between the vowel and consonant recognition performance and the SMT is logarithmic.

is equal in both experiments, it is also suggested that speech intelligibility and SMT are correlated.

With the results from Litvak et al. and Langner et al., a relation between SRT and SMT can be expected, even when they are not directly compared in their experiments.

Figure 16: The left panel is the speech intelligibility measured using the Hochmair-Schulz-Moser (HSM) sentence test and the right panel is the modulation detection threshold (SMT) using the spectral rippled noise [5]. It is shown the mean (+ symbol), the median (red line) and the 25th and 75th percentiles (rectangle and dashed line respectively) of the results. In all the cases, it was used the sequential sound coding strategy as a reference to determine how the change to paired and triplet strategies affects the performance.

Chapter 3

State-of-the-art

This chapter is a review of previous works in modeling the peripheral auditory system and the attempts of predicting hearing performance of humans using computational tools.

3.1 Peripheral auditory model for cochlear implant users

There are mainly two different approaches to model the peripheral auditory system: the "physiological" (also referred to as deterministic) based on the anatomy of the fiber and the electrode-nerve interaction in space, and the "phenomenological" (also referred to as stochastic) based on the stochastic behavior of the fibers when they are externally stimulated without considering the spatial characteristics of the electrode-nerve interface.

One challenge of physiological models is to resolve how the electrical field, produced by the electrodes in the array, interacts with the auditory nerve fibers to generate action potentials. Action potentials, due to an external voltage, occur when the neural membrane is depolarized. Once the spike is generated, the nerve membrane enters a repolarization state to recover its internal electrical characteristics followed by an hyperpolarization state where the spike generation is temporarily inhibited [28].

Figure 17 shows the stages of an action potential.

Figure 17: Action potential generated in the nerve membrane after external stimulation [28]. It shows three different stages when it is not at resting potential (-70 mV). Depolarization stage occurs when the membrane potential surpasses the threshold voltage (-55 mV) by the effect of an external stimulus. The membrane starts its repolarization stage to re-balance internal charges. The hyperpolarization occurs as a bounce effect to depolarization, inhibiting new action potentials until the membrane reaches its resting potential again.

The basic structure of the auditory nerve fiber consists of two axons and the soma. The peripheral axon extends itself towards the basilar membrane and it is the one that degenerates with time as a consequence of duration of deafness. The central axon extends itself towards the spiral ganglion. The myelinated segments on each axon have much lower conductance than the "nodes of Ranvier", meaning that in those nodes, action potentials are most probably generated by an external stimulation [2] [8]. Figure 18 shows the anatomy of a nerve fiber as described in this paragraph.

Rattay et al. (1999, 2001) modeled fiber segments as electrical circuits and applied Kirchhoff's law to the currents that appear when it is stimulated by an external potential [29] [30]. The equivalent electrical circuit is shown in Figure 19. Equation 3.1 is the applied Kirchhoff's law summing all the currents out of the node to zero. $V_{e,k}$ is the external stimulus voltage and $V_{i,k}$ the internal voltage in the segment k , R is the internal resistance of the segment and, C_m and G_m , are the external capacitance and the external conductance of the membrane m , respectively.

Figure 18: Representation of different segments presented in an auditory nerve fiber [2]. The peripheral axon is closer to the basilar membrane and it is in contact with the IHC at the peripheral terminal (node 1). The central axon lengthen towards the spiral ganglion and has several nodes not represented in this figure. The soma is where the nucleus of the neuron is located and it is surrounded by pre-somatic nodes (nodes 6, 7 and 8) and post-somatic nodes (nodes 10, 11 and 12) nodes. Myelinated segments are depicted in grey.

Figure 19: Electrical model of an auditory nerve fiber segment [29]. Every segment has an internal resistance R , an external capacitance C_m and an external conductance G_m , to form an electrical circuit with an external node $V_{e,k}$ and an internal node $V_{i,k}$.

$$C_m \frac{\delta(V_{e,k} - V_{i,k})}{\delta t} + (V_{e,k} - V_{i,k})G_m + \frac{(V_{i,k} - V_{i,k-1})}{R} + \frac{(V_{i,k} - V_{i,k+1})}{R} = 0 \quad (3.1)$$

Considering that the membrane voltage V_k is the difference between external voltage and internal voltage ($V_k = V_{e,k} - V_{i,k}$), and that the ionic currents are dependent on the membrane voltage and external conductance ($I_{ion,k} = V_k G_m$), Equation 3.1 can be rewritten as Equation 3.2.

$$\frac{\delta V_k}{\delta t} = -\frac{I_{ion,k}}{C_m} + \frac{V_{k+1} + V_{k-1} - 2V_k}{C_m R} + \frac{V_{e,k+1} + V_{e,k-1} - 2V_{e,k}}{C_m R} \quad (3.2)$$

Because R and C_m are both proportional to the segment length " a ", the denominator

$C_m R$ is proportional to the square of a ($C_m R = c_m r a^2$), where c_m and r are the conductance linear density and resistance linear density of the segment, respectively. When the segment length tends to zero ($a \rightarrow 0$), the influence of external stimulation at any point of the nerve fiber is represented by the latter term in Equation 3.2. It becomes proportional to the second derivative of the external voltage in the direction (\hat{a}) of the segment, as shown in Equation 3.3.

$$\frac{V_{e,k+1} + V_{e,k-1} - 2V_{e,k}}{c_m r a^2} \xrightarrow{a \rightarrow 0} \frac{\delta^2 V_{e,k}}{\delta \hat{a}^2} \quad (3.3)$$

This is defined by Rattay et al. as the "activation function" A_k in a given point of the auditory nerve fiber [30], as shown in Equation 3.4. This is important because, depending on the model used, the factor multiplying this second derivative may vary. The activation function units must be Volts divided by seconds [V/s] to be consistent with Equation 3.2.

$$A_k = \frac{1}{c_m r} \frac{\delta^2 V_{e,k}}{\delta \hat{a}_k^2} \quad (3.4)$$

This physiological model of the auditory nerve fiber was included by Nogueira et al. (2016) in a three-dimensional representation of the cochlea with an implanted electrode array as part of the IndiMoCI project. The IndiMoCI model also includes electrical characteristics of the inner parts of the cochlea to compute precisely the potential spread generated by the electrodes using the Equation 3.5, where $V_{n,a}$ is the voltage induced by the electrode n at the point a in space, I is the stimulus current out of the electrode, G is the total inner conductance in the cochlea, and (x, y, z) are the Cartesian coordinates of a given point in space [31].

$$V_{n,a} = \frac{I}{4\pi G \sqrt{(x_n - x_a)^2 + (y_n - y_a)^2 + (z_n - z_a)^2}} \quad (3.5)$$

The dimensions of the cochlea were based on clinical imaging data, so it was possible to individualize the model to a specific patient. Figure 20 shows the IndiMoCI

electrode-nerve interface with 201 fibers in red and the electrode array in blue.

Figure 20: Projection in the plane xy of the three-dimensional representation of fibers (red) and electrodes (blue) inside the cochlea model developed in the IndiMoCI project. In this figure, there are only 201 fibers, but the model is capable of generating up to 9001 nerve fibers

Currently, the model consist of 9001 fibers, but because of the computational power required to compute the membrane voltage in every segment of every fiber, the IndiMoCI model takes into consideration only one "activation point". Its location is controlled by a variable b_f , ranging from 0 to 1 ($0 \leq b_f \leq 1$), representing the degeneration of the fiber f . When $b_f = 0$, the activation point correspond to a location close to the spiral ganglion, and when $b_f = 1$, corrspond to a location close to the basilar membrane. This mechanism is shown in Figure 21.

The activation function A_{fn} at the activation point is computed using Equations 3.4 and 3.5 resulting in Equation 3.6, where d is the distance between the electrode n and the activation point a_f . \hat{a} and \hat{d} are unitary vectors in the direction of the fiber

Figure 21: Degeneration mechanism implemented in the IndiMoCI model. The red dot is the activation point, the fiber is represented in a red line with the degenerated part dashed. d is the distance between the electrode and the activation point.

at a_f and d , respectively.

$$A_{fn} = \frac{I}{4\pi Gc_m r} \left(3 \frac{(\hat{a}_f \cdot d\hat{d}_{fn})^2}{d^5} - \frac{1}{d^3} \right) \quad (3.6)$$

This version of the IndiMoCI model was used to study the effects of nerve degeneration by reproducing eCAP responses virtually [2].

In a phenomenological model, the auditory nerve fiber is represented as a whole, without dimensions, with an stochastic response to an external stimulus. Because of this, those models are less demanding in terms of computational power while being completely reliable to represent empirical data.

Bruce et al. (1999) proposed a simple stochastic model that depends directly on the activation function A_f [32]. It was used by Litvak et al. (2007) to study loudness growth in a tripolar stimulation mode [33], and by Nogueira et al. (2016) with the IndiMoCI project to study neural activity of fibers in different settings of the three-dimensional electrode-nerve interface [31]. Neural activity is defined as the amount

of spikes generated in a group of fibers by an external stimulus. The model of Bruce et al. represents fairly well the overall neural activity, but, as mentioned in Chapter 2, temporal information is also important and it is not considered.

Hamacher (2004) proposed a model where a refractory period, latency and jitter was considered to enhance the representation in time of the spike activity. The nerve membrane is modeled as a leaky integrate-and-fire electrical circuit, where membrane voltage is calculated in time steps depending on: an external stimulation current, an internal noise source that introduces stochasticity, and feedback currents for stabilization. The spike is generated once a voltage threshold is reached [34]. This model allowed Fredelake et al. (2012) and Jürgens et al. (2018) to simulate more complex experiments as speech-in-noise perception [25] [35].

Joshi et al. (2017) proposed a more physiologically inspired model, where it is considered that the fiber has different characteristics in the central and peripheral axon, as shown in Figure 22. Axons are modeled as two independent leaky integrate-and-fire circuits, with their own current feedback (sub-threshold and supra-threshold) and their own noise source. Also, it is based on the observations that the central axon is stimulated by the anodic part and inhibited by the cathodic part of the stimulus current, contrary to the peripheral axon that is stimulated by the cathodic part and inhibited by the anodic part of the stimulus current. The "OR gate" at the model's output detects whenever one of the axons produces a spike. Once a spike is generated, the whole fiber enters in an absolute refractory period (ARP) where spikes are completely inhibited in both axons [19].

The membrane voltage V of each axon in the Joshi et al. model is calculated through Equation 3.7, where C is membrane capacitance, t is time, $h(V)$ is a passive filter dependent on membrane voltage, I_{Sub} and I_{Supra} are internal adaptation currents in the membrane, I_{Noise} is a noise current source with a Gaussian spectral shape, and I_{Stim} is the axon stimulation current.

$$C \frac{\delta V}{\delta t} = h(V) - I_{Sub} - I_{Supra} + I_{Noise} + I_{Stim} \quad (3.7)$$

Figure 22: Auditory nerve fiber electrical model divided in two axons with independent noise source, sub-threshold feedback, and supra-threshold feedback [19]. The "OR gate" unifies the two axons spike trains into a single one.

The passive filter $h(V)$ depends on membrane electrical characteristics as internal conductance g_L , a slope factor ΔT , the resting potential E_L , and the threshold v_t , as shown in Equation 3.8.

$$h(V) = g_L \left(E_L + \Delta T \exp \frac{V - v_t}{\Delta T} - V \right) \quad (3.8)$$

The adaptation currents I_{Sub} and I_{Supra} are updated with their respective differential equations 3.9 and 3.10, where τ are time constants, and a_{Sub} and a_{Supra} are external conductance.

$$\tau_{Sub} \frac{\delta I_{Sub}}{\delta t} = a_{Sub} (V - E_L) - I_{Sub} \quad (3.9)$$

$$\tau_{Supra} \frac{\delta I_{Supra}}{\delta t} = a_{Supra} (V - E_L) - I_{Supra} \quad (3.10)$$

The spectral shape of the noise is equal to $1/f^\alpha$, where f is frequency and α is spectral decay.

Finally, the axon stimulation current I_{stim} is different for both axons to make them respond accordingly to the anodic and the cathodic phase of the current stimulus as shown in Equation 3.11, where I^- is the cathodic part and I^+ is the anodic part of the stimulus current I . A factor β , between 0 and 1 ($0 \leq \beta \leq 1$), is added to control the amount of inhibition of the opposite phase, being $\beta = 0$ none and $\beta = 1$ total inhibition.

$$I_{stim} = \begin{cases} -(I^- + \beta I^+) & \text{Peripheral axon} \\ I^+ + \beta I^- & \text{Central axon} \end{cases} \quad (3.11)$$

3.2 Computational tools for simulated auditory experiments

To predict CI users performance in any auditory task with a computational tool, features cannot be extracted from the audio signal directly, but from the spike activity, which is the spike train from all fibers in the peripheral auditory model. This is the reason why some computational tools like DeepSpeech [36] or WaveNet [37] cannot be directly implemented to perform speech recognition experiments for CI users. The best option is to use a tool designed to work directly with the spike activity or features extracted from them.

A very simple tool, used by Fredelake et al. (2012) to predict speech performance of CI users, is the dynamic time warping (DTW) classifier. An algorithm performed spatial and temporal integration of the spike activity to obtain an internal representation (IR). Fredelake et al. built a database with the IR of the 50 words in the OLSA matrix mixed at different SNRs. Then, performed a matrix sentence test using the DTW algorithms to find the best match between the target sentence and words in the database. Although the DTW classifier performed well, it is not more

efficient than machine learning tools [35].

Hidden Markov models (HMMs) and neural networks are currently the most used methods for speech related tasks. The HMM toolkit (HTK) has been used for long time in speech recognition and there is plenty of documentation available online [38]. In the other hand, there are neural networks that learn directly from the spike activity of simulated neurons known as "spiking neural networks" (SNNs) and have been used for sound classification by Wu et al. [39].

Recently, a tool for auditory experiments has been proposed, the simulation framework for auditory discrimination experiments (FADE). The project was born in 2016 in the Carl von Ossietzky University of Oldenburg, which is part of the Hearing4All (H4A) cluster of excellence [40]. The most relevant characteristics of this framework is that it performs speech recognition tasks and psychoacoustic experiments using a common set of parameters in the back-end prediction tool, which is HTK [4].

The framework has been capable to reproduce, and hence predict, human performance in tone-in-noise detection and speech-in-noise recognition [4]. It has been extended by Kollmeier et al. (2016) to build a model for hearing impaired listeners [3], later used by Schädler et al. (2018) to study the benefits of noise-reduction algorithms in hearing aids [41]. Finally, it has been used for CI speech-in-noise experiments by Jürgens et al. (2018) [25]. Figure 23 shows a block diagram of a SRT experiment for hearing impaired people using FADE.

The HMM consists of a collection of "Markov chains" corresponding to every type of stimulus or word that needs to be recognized in the experiment. For example, in SRT experiments there would be 50 Markov chains, each one representing one word in the matrix, and in SMT experiments there would be only two Markov chains representing the reference noise and the spectral rippled noise. The Markov chains used by FADE are always a left-to-right probabilistic network of eight states that have the probability p_{xx} to stay in the state x or p_{xy} to advance to the next state y , every time frame. It also has an initial (*INIT*) and a final (*END*) state located at the extremes of the chain, as shown in Figure 24. Every state in the Markov chain is

Figure 23: Block diagram of the simulation framework for auditory discrimination experiments (FADE) [41]. In the grey block is depicted a speech reception threshold (SRT) experiment, which is common to a human participant as well. The speech (S) is mixed with noise (N) at a certain signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). The signal is processed by a hearing aid algorithm that emulates the hearing condition of a given participant. Then features are extracted from the processed signal and recognized by a hidden Markov model (HMM). The process is repeated for different sentences at different SNRs to obtain the psychometric function.

a Gaussian mixture model (GMM) of one component, meaning that the probability of occurrence depends on a "mean" and a "variance" value of the observable features [4].

Figure 24: An eight state Markov chain used by the HTK toolkit to represent a stimulus or a single word. Every state has the probability to stay p_{xx} in the state x or to advance p_{xy} to the state y every time step. The *INIT* and *END* states only indicate where the Markov chain starts and finishes.

When the HMM is being trained, there are no time stamps for the HTK to know exactly when the stimulus or sentence is occurring, and that is why FADE is referred to as a reference-free tool [3] [4]. The only temporal clue is the "grammar", so Schädler et al. defined four more special Markov chains to detect border artifacts.

The *START* and *END* chains, consisting of only three states, learn the beginning and the end of every file. The *PRE_SIL* and *POST_SIL* chains, consisting of six states, learn the signal before and after the stimulus or sentence of every file. This grammar is shown in Figure 25.

Figure 25: Representation of the reference grammar used by HTK to locate the target stimulus or sentence in an audio file. *START* and *END* are the boundaries of the file, while *PRE_SIL* and *POST_SIL* are the signal previous and posterior to the target sentence or stimulus. Notice that in this figure the audio wave is shown as a simplification, but the HMM actually looks at the different features extracted from it.

At the beginning of the training procedure, the GMM mean and variance of every Markov chain is set to the overall mean and variance of the observable features along all the training corpus. Every file is labeled and the GMM of every Markov chain is updated in eight epoques of training [4].

When the HMM is used for recognition, the same grammar structure is expected. The predicted sentence or stimulus is obtained by an algorithm that searches the most probable combination of Markov chains [38], as represented in Figure 26. The recognition time depends on how many possible combinations exist, so an advantage of using the OLSA matrix sentence test is that the prediction algorithm searches over a very limited scope of words.

FADE is designed to run on a Linux operative system (OS), and consists of a collection of ".bash" files and project templates. Those files and templates contain the code to execute an experiment from the generation of the corpus to the performance

Figure 26: Selection of the most probable Markov chain. The probability of occurrence is a combination of how observable features match the Gaussian mixture model (GMM) and the probabilities of staying or advancing every time frame.

evaluation. By default, the experiments done by Schädler et al. can be replicated with the original files in the repository [42], but it also allows the modification of algorithms and some configuration files to be adjusted to the needs of new experiments without modifying the core code of the framework. Some of the possible modifications are:

- The configuration file with training and testing conditions
- The configuration file with corpus generation conditions
- The configuration file with some HTK parameters (number of states of the Markov chains, number of epoques for training)
- The algorithm to generate a training and a testing corpus
- The algorithm to process the corpus
- The algorithm to extract features from a corpus
- The algorithm to generate figures or tables from obtained results

It is important to mention that these algorithms are preferred to be written in MATLAB or Octave language. The HTK should be already installed and working

in the computer to perform an experiment. Another important consideration to take into account when modifying or replacing the feature extraction algorithm, is that the framework is expecting features every 10 ms to train the HMM.

3.3 Speech-in-noise prediction models for cochlear implant users

The first computational model capable of performing speech recognition was developed by Nogueira et al. in 2007. Two N-of-M CI sound coding strategies were compared with such a model. The electrode-nerve interface consisted in a spread function that stimulates 211 sections of the cochlea. Each section was associated to a width of 0.1 Bark covering from 5 Hz to 8 kHz. A HMM was used as the prediction tool, but to reduce the amount of data it was implemented a discrete cosine transform (DCT) to obtain the CI cepstral coefficients (CICCs) [43]. Only the first 12 CICCs were used to build a set of 37 features in total [9].

In 2012, Fredelake et al. built a computational model capable of running a speech-in-noise prediction task. Previously it was mentioned that a DTW classifier was used as the prediction tool and the input was the OLSA matrix sentence test mixed at different SNRs. The electrodiagram representation of the sentences was generated by a N-of-M sound coding strategy [35], which is another variation of the CIS sound coding strategy where only N electrodes out of M available are activated per cycle [44].

The electrode-nerve interface is built in a uni-dimensional space. Up to 10 thousand auditory nerves are arranged uniformly in a 35-mm line and 22 electrodes were located 0,75 mm apart from each other in the middle of the nerve array. The spatial spread of the electrical field generated by the electrodes over the nerve cells is calculated with an exponential function inversally proportional to the distance between electrodes and nerve cells. The rate of decrement is parameterized by a factor λ . The bigger the value of λ , the wider the electrical field spread and more cells are stimulated by a single electrode. Their peripheral auditory model is based

on the Hamacher's model [35]. Figure 27 shows a block diagram of the complete auditory model proposed by Fredelake et al.

Figure 27: Auditory model used by Fredelake et al. to study the performance of CI users [35]. The model consists of a uni-dimensional electrode-nerve interface with an exponential spatial spread function. The peripheral model consists of a group of, up to 10 thousand, auditory nerves generating a spike activity. It is integrated in space and time in the central auditory processing to obtain an internal representation (IR) of the sounds. The IR is used as features in the DTW classifier.

The central auditory processing is an integration in space and time to obtain the IR of the spike activity generated by the auditory nerves. The steps to obtain the IR are listed as follows:

1. Downsample the spike activity to 5 kHz
2. Perform a spatial integration by summing spike trains of neighbour auditory nerves to obtain the "group activity" (SPG). The auditory nerves were integrated in 46 groups with respect to the closest electrode in the array. The most basal and apical nerves were limited to groups of 0.75-mm wide
3. Apply a low-pass filter to the signal to obtain the "average group activity" (SR) as shown in Equation 3.12, where g is the group index, k is the discrete time, f_s is sample frequency and τ_{LP1} is the time constant of the low-pass filter

4. Perform a non-linear integration in time applying a recursive low-pass filter to SR and obtain the internal state (Z) that acts as a masker signal as shown in Equation 3.13, where the coefficients c_1 and c_2 are calculated by the equation 3.14. τ_{att} and τ_{rel} are the attack and release time of the filter, respectively
5. Obtain the internal representation (IR) as the maximum instant value between SR and Z ($IR_g(k) = \max[SR_g(k), Z_g(k)]$). The masking effect is shown in Figure 28.
6. Smooth the IR with another recursive low-pass filter.

$$SR_g(k) = SPG_g(k) \exp \left(- \left(\frac{k}{\sqrt{2}f_s\tau_{LP1}} \right)^2 \right) \quad (3.12)$$

$$Z_g(k) = c_1(k)Z_g(k-1) + c_2(k)SR_g(k) \quad (3.13)$$

$$\begin{cases} c_1(k) = \exp \left(- \frac{1}{\tau_{att}f_s} \right), c_2(k) = 1 - c_1(k) & \text{for } SR_g(k) \geq Z_g(k-1) \\ c_1(k) = \exp \left(- \frac{1}{\tau_{rel}f_s} \right), c_2(k) = 0 & \text{for } SR_g(k) < Z_g(k-1) \end{cases} \quad (3.14)$$

In 2018, Jürgens et al. used this model to individualize its performance according to measurements of the electrical potential spread function for different CI user and an internal noise variable that depends on their cognition capabilities [25]. The structure of the model is shown in Figure 29.

The difference with the Fredelake et al. model is that the spatial spread function was adapted to every participant instead of having the exponential function and the IR was multiplied by the internal noise to emulate the cognitive capacities of the participant. Jürgens et al. also compared the performance of FADE and the DTW classifier.

Figure 28: Representation of the masking effect proposed by Fredelake et al. (2012) [35]. The signal $Z(k)$ is the internal state of the group of fiber k representing the adaptation of the auditory system to the average group activity $SR(k)$. The internal representation $IR(k)$ will be the greater value between $Z(k)$ and $SR(k)$ in every instance. The masking effect is shown in the right panel where the second pulse of $SR(k)$ is not high enough to surpass $Z(k)$, hence is not affecting the resulting $IR(k)$.

Figure 29: Computational model built by Jürgens et al. (2018) [25]. The auditory model is similar to the Fredelake et al. model but the DTW classifier is substituted by FADE, an internal noise parameter was added to emulate cognitive skills.

The computational model of Jürgens et al. is the first one to perform a prediction experiment on FADE using a CI sound coding strategy and an auditory model, but they found no correlation between the predicted and real performance regarding

the electrical potential spread functions. It was argued that the neural health of the participants were not taken into account and it could play an important role in speech recognition tasks.

Chapter 4

Design of the computational model

In this chapter it is described the structure of the proposed computational model, preliminary experiments, and results obtained in the designing process. The model is divided in three parts: the front-end containing the CI sound coding strategy and the peripheral auditory model, the adapter as the feature extractor, and the back-end prediction tool, as shown in Figure 30.

Figure 30: Block diagram of the proposed computational model. The stimulus or word is processed by a sound coding strategy and a peripheral auditory model in the front-end to obtain the spike activity. The adapter performs a feature extraction to the spike activity to obtain an internal representation. The back-end uses FADE as the prediction tool to recognize the presented word or stimulus.

4.1 Front-end

The front-end consists of a sound coding strategy algorithm and the peripheral auditory model. The stimuli or speech is presented in a ".wav" format normalized to -49 dB full scale [dB_{FS}], that corresponds to an acoustic signal at 65 dB sound

pressure level [dB_{SPL}] captured by the microphone of the CI device. At this level, the stimulus signal is not affected by internal dynamic controls of the CI audio processor.

As mentioned before, the sound coding strategy F120 is used in the experiments with three different pulse tables resulting in three sound coding strategies (F120-S, F120-P and F120-T). Because the mapping is needed for the strategy to generate electrodiagrams, a file with the average mapping of 12 individuals is generated for each sound coding strategy.

The proposed peripheral auditory model is an implementation of the phenomenological auditory nerve model proposed by Joshi et al. (2017) as a substitute of the physiological model already implemented in the IndiMoCI electrode-nerve interface [19] [31]. The principal issue is that the Joshi et al. model and the IndiMoCI interface cannot be directly connected. The phenomenological model uses current in Amperes [A] as input (see Equations 3.7 and 3.11), while the IndiMoCI model is designed to compute the activation function in Volts per second [V/s] at a given activation point, as shown previously in Figure 21 and Equation 3.6. To overcome this limitation, a relation between the stimulus current I_{Stim} and activation function A_f has to be found.

Since Rattay equation 3.2 and Joshi et al. model equation 3.7 represent the membrane voltage as a first order differential equation, they are equivalent, as shown in Equation 4.1. The ionic currents $I_{ion,k}$ from Equation 3.2 and the feedback currents I_{Sub} and I_{Supra} from Equation 3.7 are representations of adaptation currents between the exterior and the interior of the nerve cell and both depend on the membrane voltage.

$$-\frac{I_{ion,k}}{C_m} \equiv -I_{Sub} - I_{Supra} \quad (4.1)$$

The second term of Equation 3.2, the passive filter, and the noise current of Equation 3.7 ($h(V)$ and I_{Noise}) are representations of internal currents that depend on the

membrane internal conductance. Hence Equation 4.2 shows another equivalency.

$$\frac{V_{k+1} + V_{k-1} - 2V_k}{C_m R} \equiv h(v) + I_{Noise} \quad (4.2)$$

The last term of Equation 3.2 depends only on the external voltage $V_{e,k}$, and the external voltage is proportional to the electrode stimulus current I , as shown in Equation 3.5, so it is representing the same phenomenon as the variable I_{Stim} in Equation 3.7. This equivalency is represented in Equation 4.3.

$$\frac{V_{e,k+1} + V_{e,k-1} - 2V_{e,k}}{C_m R} \equiv I_{Stim} \quad (4.3)$$

Finally, writing Equation 4.3 in terms of the activation function A_f , following the Equations 3.4 and 3.6, and I_{Stim} as in Equation 3.11, Equation 4.4 is obtained, where M_f is a modelling factor that is manually calibrated to normalize the firing probabilities according to Joshi et al. experiments [19]. Its unit should be Faraday [F] to preserve the unit consistency of the equation.

$$I_{Stim,n} = \frac{M_f}{4\pi G c_m r} \left(3 \frac{(\hat{a}_f \cdot d\hat{d}_{fn})^2}{d^5} - \frac{1}{d^3} \right) \cdot \begin{cases} -(I^- + \beta I^+) & \text{Peripheral axon} \\ I^+ + \beta I^- & \text{Central axon} \end{cases} \quad (4.4)$$

This equation is just for one electrode "n" of the array, thus the total stimulus current over a single fiber is the sum of the whole electrode array (when simultaneous stimulation), as shown in Equation 4.5, where N is the number of electrodes.

$$I_{Stim} = \sum_{n=1}^N I_{Stim,n} \quad (4.5)$$

Depending on the location of the electrodes, the activation point shown in Figure 21 is not necessarily the most likely place to generate a spike in the nerve fiber, so

the nodes in both axons are taken into account as well. Figure 18 shows that fibers are modeled with five nodes per axon (nodes 1 to 5 in the peripheral axon and 13 to 17 in the central axon). These axons are identified in Figure 31, and their nodes in Figure 32. The activation function is computed at the activation point and at all nodes that are still available after applying degeneration. The place with the maximum activation function absolute value is selected as the stimulation point, since it is the most likely place to generate spikes.

Figure 31: Representation of the peripheral axon, the soma, and the central axon in the IndiMoCI model for each auditory nerve. Only 201 fibers are represented.

In Figures 33 and 34 the stimulation is shown, in terms of the second derivative by distance [$1/m^3$], of all electrodes over all the fibers in the IndiMoCI model with no degeneration and full degeneration respectively. Note that without degeneration, certain spectral resolution is achieved at the base of the cochlea (fibers 1 to 4500), while with degeneration the resolution is lost and stimulation levels are lower.

For every fiber, the spike train is computed resulting in the spike activity of the whole peripheral model, which represents the input of the feature extractor. The

Figure 32: Nodes, or unmyelinated segments, in the peripheral and central axon of a single fiber.

temporal resolution is the closer value to $1 \mu s$ that can represent the symmetry of the biphasic pulses for the electrodiagram stimulation rate.

4.2 Feature extractor

The feature extraction is based on the central auditory processing used by Fredelake et al. [35]. As described in Section 3.3, it is an integration in space and time to obtain the IR following six steps. Some adjustments were done to this central auditory processing in the proposed model. First, the spike activity is downsampled to 10 kHz instead of 5 kHz to increment the temporal resolution when extracting features. Secondly, because the electrode-nerve interface is different, a new grouping algorithm was implemented inspired by the auditory filters that are present in the basilar membrane to code complex sounds. And finally, because the recursive low-

Figure 33: Activation function in $[1/m^3]$ (y-axis) over nerve fibers (x-axis being 1 the most basal fiber) without degeneration. Each color represents one electrode. In this case, the stimulation at the base of the cochlea depicts bell shaped functions meaning that the electrodes are stimulating mostly a limited group of fibers.

pass filter mentioned in the sixth step was not described by Fredelake et al., the convolutional low-pass filter of the third step was used again to smooth the IR.

The algorithm to form the groups of fibers in the spatial integration calculates the cochlea length C_L by integrating the distance along the most peripheral points of the fibers, which are in contact with the basilar membrane. Next, it defines a maximum and a minimum length for the auditory filters AF_L depending on the maximum number of filters that can be formed ($NAF = 39$) and the number of electrodes N in the array according to Equation 4.6. This is based on Moores's publication (2003) about coding sounds in NH people and CI users [7].

$$\frac{C_L}{NAF} \leq AF_L \leq \frac{C_L}{N} \quad (4.6)$$

Then, the algorithm compares the activation function of each electrode over every fiber and classifies them by the number of the electrode n_e that provides the highest

Figure 34: Activation function in $[1/m^3]$ (y-axis) over the nerve fibers (x-axis being 1 the most basal fiber) with total nerve degeneration. Each color represents one electrode. The overall stimulation distribution is irregular causing loss of spectral resolution.

stimulation. The groups are consecutive fibers that have the same n_e value(s), with a length bounded by the Equation 4.6. Figure 35 shows the groups formed when there is no degeneration.

Although the IR can be used as a feature to train a HMM because it is similar to a spectrogram-like representation of the firing rate [25], features more specific to human perception of sounds could be derived from it. Nogueira applied a discrete cosine transform (DCT) to compute what he called cochlear implant cepstral coefficients (CICCs), which is an analogy to the mel-frequency cepstral coefficients (MFCCs) and the spectrogram of an audio signal [9]. CICCs carry information related to loudness of the signal and spectral shape of the IR along the groups.

Another approach is to emulate the information used by the brain for coding sounds. Wouters et al. (2015) mention three categories for temporal speech information in three different frequency bands [20]. The first of these bands is in the range between 2 and 20 Hz, where the speech envelopes are perceived as fluctuations in the overall

Figure 35: Groups formed in the spatial integration of the spike activity in the feature extraction algorithm. The boundaries of the groups are depicted in dashed black lines and they are formed depending on the electrode that most stimulates the fibers. Its lengths are bounded to obtain between N and 39 channels, being N the number of electrodes in the array.

amplitude of the signal. These fluctuations are well represented by the IR.

Bellow 2 Hz, it is obtained the average firing rate of each group of fibers and two other important features could be extracted. The first one, by integrating the firing rate along all the groups of fibers to obtain a value related to the overall loudness [12]. The second one, by obtaining the relative firing rate along the groups which is related to the perception of timbre [7].

Finally, above 20 Hz, the IR carries information about spike periodicity at least for frequencies between 50 and 500 Hz where the fundamental frequency of the speech is commonly located [20]. This periodicity is also closely related to the phase locking when perceiving pitch, as shown in Figure 4 [7] [11]. One way to obtain this periodicity is by applying a fast Fourier transform (FFT) to the overall high-pass filtered IR. The three higher spectral peaks found correspond to three possible frequencies that are being phase locked.

Figure 36 shows a complete diagram of the features proposed in this section. The temporal integration and the hop size of the FFT were set to 10 ms to be compatible with FADE specifications. The spatial integration means that all channels were summed into one dimension. If there is no spatial integration, the feature is N -dimensional with N being the number of groups. The output of the peak detection has three dimensions corresponding to each peak detected.

Figure 36: Block diagram of the proposed set of features that are computed from the internal representation (IR). The first one is the raw IR but integrated across 10 ms. The cochlear implant cepstral coefficients (CICCs) are obtained applying a discrete cosine transform (DCT) to the IR after the temporal integration. The overall firing rate represents the overall loudness and it is the integration in space and time of the IR filtered below 2 Hz. The relative firing rate is the representation of the relative loudness among auditory filters of the normalized and low-pass filtered IR. The fluctuations in overall amplitude are the temporal modulations of the IR between the range of 2 and 20 Hz, as it is found in speech. The spike periodicity is the spiking rate found in the IR, it detects if there is phase locking in frequencies above 20 Hz, by applying a FFT with a hop size of 10 ms. The peak locator obtains the three most higher peaks in the spectrum of the IR.

It is important to mention that these features emulate some processes occurring in the central auditory system, but they are not intended to model it as done by the peripheral auditory system in this work. For such a reason, the experiments are executed using only the IR first, and then, all the features are incorporated to investigate if there is an improvement in performance.

4.3 Back-end and experiment procedure

In FADE, two project templates were created: one to perform SRT experiments, and the second to perform SMT experiments. In both cases, the F120 sound coding strategy is implemented as the processing algorithm and the proposed peripheral auditory model with the adapter as the feature extraction algorithm.

For SRT experiments, the corpus was generated from a set of 100 different OLSA sentences chosen such that each of the 50 words of the matrix appears exactly 10 times. A random excerpt of the *Comité Consultatif International Téléphonique et Télégraphique* (CCITT) noise is added to the sentences at the required level to obtain the different SNRs, while the speech is kept at -49 dB_{FS} . The training corpus consisted of eight sets of the OLSA sentences at 0, 3, 6, 9, 12, 15, 18, and infinite dB_{SNR} , respectively, giving a total of 80 unique instances for each word. The testing corpus consisted of ten sets of the OLSA sentences at values between -9 and 18 dB_{SNR} in steps of 3 dB respectively, giving a total of 5000 words to be predicted at 10 different SNR conditions.

For SMT experiments, the corpus was generated using a MATLAB code. The spectral ripple noise shape is obtained using Equation 2.1 with a random ripple phase θ_0 and $RPO = 0.5$ to be consistent with the experiments of Litvak et al. (2007) [26] and Langner et al. (2017) [5]. The training corpus consisted of 80 samples of the spectral ripple noise with random integer values between 2 and 20 for contrast depth ($2 \leq Ct \leq 20$) and 80 samples of reference noise ($Ct = 0$). The testing corpus consisted of ten sets, each one with 250 samples of reference noise and 250 samples of spectral ripple noise at a target contrast depth Ct_{set} . The Ct_{set} values were 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 9, 11, 14, 17, and 20 dB, respectively. In total 5000 samples are predicted in 10 different Ct conditions.

The processing algorithm took the corpus generated in ".wav" format to compute a corpus of electrograms in MATLAB ".mat" files. A file containing the pulse table information and the individual mapping of the electrodes should be manually located in a specific folder inside the project directory, which was automatically

created when the project was initialized.

The feature extraction algorithm took corpus of electrodiagrams and generated a corpus of ".htk" files ready to be used by the HTK toolkit. The majority of the code was written in MATLAB, except for the auditory nerve model that was written in C++ and compiled with NVIDIA nvcc as a ".ptx" file. This run a kernel inside a NVIDIA graphic processing unit (GPU) to process the 9001 fibers of the peripheral auditory model in parallel, reducing the execution time of each experiment considerably. All the information of the geometry of the cochlea (i.e., position of the electrodes, position of the fibers and its degeneration state) was manually located in a specific folder inside the project directory as well.

Once the HMMs were trained and tested, the percentage of correct predictions at every SNR or Ct condition was calculated and represented as points in a chart (data). Then a non-linear regression was implemented using the MATLAB function "fitnlm" (version 2019a) with the psychometric function defined in Equation 4.7, where p_{chance} is the chance probability of the experiment (50% for SMT predictions and 10% for SRT predictions), p_{range} is the difference between the top performance p_{max} and p_{chance} ($p_{chance} < p_{max} \leq 1$), s is the slope, or growth rate, at the inflection point of the psychometric function, and x_o is the offset of the inflection point in the x-axis. The x-axis is given in $[dB_{SNR}]$ for SRT experiments and $[dB_{Ct}]$ for SMT experiments.

$$fr(x) = p_{chance} + \frac{p_{range}}{1 + e^{-s(x-x_o)}} \quad (4.7)$$

The coefficient of determination (R^2) was also provided by the MATLAB function *fitnlm*, and it was used as reference of how well the "data" represented the regressed probabilistic function. Because $fr(x)$ is a statistical model of the data, the confidence intervals are obtained by a chi-squared distribution χ^2 equal to 3.84. All the data points inside these "chance boundaries" fr_b have an statistical significance equivalent to a p_value of 0.05 or less. See Equation 4.8 where N is the number of

samples predicted ($N = 500$ in both experiments) [45] [46].

$$fr_b^2(x) - 2fr(x)fr_b(x) + fr^2(x) - \frac{\chi^2 fr(x)(1 - fr(x))}{N} = 0 \quad (4.8)$$

The SRT was defined as the x value where $fr(x) = 50\%$ and the SMT as the x value where $fr(x) = 79.4\%$. Figure 37 shows an example of the non-linear regression of the results in a SRT experiment.

4.4 Notes on the testing methodology

Schädler et al. originally proposed a methodology to evaluate the performance consisting of training various HMMs at a single condition value with FADE. Following that approach, 10 different models are obtained, which should be trained with their respective single condition, tested with the same data, and instead of having one single psychometric function, it is obtained one function per condition. This is shown in Figure 38, where 11 SNR conditions were trained and the model with the lowest SRT was chosen as the predictor.

Thus, the consequence of using the original approach is the huge amount of data obtained that had to be processed, hence the execution time of the experiments would increase considerably. With the proposed methodology, a complete SRT experiment was executed in around 37 hours and a SMT experiment in around 17 hours. In addition to that, when the model is trained at a single SNR, it shows an overfitting to the training condition, as shown in Figure 39. This behavior was not found in any previous experiments using FADE [3] [4] [25] [41], meaning that with the original methodology the model is not capable of identifying noise at SNR levels that have not been used in the training corpus. The proposed methodology was able to do that.

To avoid such drawbacks in execution time and overfitting, the new methodology of evaluation described in the previous section was implemented and corresponding modifications to the original code of the framework were made.

Figure 37: Regression function (blue line) of the data (circles) obtained in an SRT experiment. The SRT (red cross) is the SNR value where the regression function crosses the 50% score. The predicted top performance is shown with the horizontal red line. The "chance boundaries" (dashed lines) are the limits where the data have a significance equivalent to a p_value of 0.05. This is the result obtained using the 9001 fibers of the IndiMoCI model, without degeneration of the nerves and using the F120-S pulse table.

Figure 38: Original methodology of evaluation with FADE [4]. The left chart represents the results obtained with the HMM trained at every condition and the 50% crossing is shown by the black and white line. Training at -3 dB_{SNR} resulted in the best performance, so that is the model used to predict the SRT as shown in the right chart.

Figure 39: Example of the result obtained when the model is trained at a 9 dB_{SNR} only (with original methodology). Note that the maximum performance (Data) is obtained for the training SNR and then it decreases in both directions. The R^2 coefficient decreased meaning that the psychometric function does not fit the data obtained

Chapter 5

Experiment results

Using the proposed computational model, a total of 18 SRT experiments and 18 SMT experiments were executed. The amount of experiments resulted from all the possible combination of the following parameters:

- The CI sound coding strategies:
 - Sequential (F120-S)
 - Paired (F120-P)
 - Triplet (F120-T)
- The auditory nerve condition. Varying the parameters b_f and nerve count of the IndiMoCI model as described in Figure 21:
 - No degeneration ($b_f = 1$, 9001 fibers)
 - Low count of fibers ($b_f = 1$, 2251 fibers)
 - Fibers fully degenerated ($b_f = 0$, 9001 fibers)
- Training and testing features:
 - Only IR
 - All features described in Section 4.2

A generic geometry file with cochlea dimensions and electrode positions in the electrode-nerve interface was used throughout all the experiments.

To obtain a good interpretation of the results on how each of these parameters influenced the performance, they are organized in the following sections. The individual figures obtained from each of the 36 experiments are shown in Appendix A.

The experiments were performed in a computer with Ubuntu 18.04 OS. The parallel computing was executed in an NVIDIA GPU unit Tesla K40c.

5.1 Speech reception threshold performance

The SRT experiment results are divided into two groups, the first one using only IR as features and the second one using all the features described in Section 4.2. Each group has a corresponding table with the SRT, the predicted top performance p_{max} , and the growth rate of the curve s at the inflection point. Tables are organized by nerve condition and sound coding strategy. Best results are considered when SRT is the lowest, p_{max} is the closest to 100%, and the slope s is the steepest because it means a greater rate of improvement when increasing the SNR. Those values are highlighted with a ***bold-italic*** font in such tables.

Four experiments resulted in a psychometric function with a predicted top performance below the 50% threshold, so the SRT is labeled as "not applicable" (N/A) in its respective tables. The R^2 coefficient was greater than 0.90 in all cases with a valid SRT result, meaning that the proposed psychometric function equation 4.7 is a good representation of the data, which is at the same time, comparable to the CI users performance as described by Wagener et al. (1999) [23] and shown in Figure 13.

Table 2 shows the results using only IR as features. In general, the SRTs correspond to a very poor CI user performance compared to the data from Jürgens et al. (2018) [25]. There is also a gap of more than 30% between the 100% score and the top performance. The gap increases with the larger fiber degeneration. This means that the HMM may require more epochs for training, more training data, or perform

on higher SNRs.

Table 2: Results from SRT experiments using only IR as features.

Only IR as features		Sequential	Paired	Triplet
No Degeneration	SRT [dB]	10.19	10.48	9.00
	p_{max} [%]	65.28	63.26	67.83
	s [%/dB]	0.60	0.69	0.91
Low count of fibers	SRT [dB]	11.18	10.12	9.04
	p_{max} [%]	66.49	64.24	64.93
	s [%/dB]	0.48	0.67	0.90
Fibers fully degenerated	SRT [dB]	N/A	N/A	N/A
	p_{max} [%]	23.97	25.63	27.10
	s [%/dB]	1.54	0.21	0.25

Looking at the sound coding strategies, Figure 40 shows the psychometric functions obtained using only IR as features and no degeneration of the fibers. The confidence intervals of sequential and paired strategies are clearly intercepting each other meaning that their difference is not significant. Triplet strategy obtained better results in all the nerve conditions tested, with a clear difference comparing to the other two sound coding strategies. This is contrary to the empiric results found by Langner et al. (2017) shown in Figure 16, where sequential and paired got similar results while triplet strategy clearly worsen the CI user performance [5]. There are some hypothesis that could explain this contradiction, that will be discussed in the next chapter.

Table 3 shows the results using all the features. The performance improved compared to the results presented in Table 2, but SMTs still correspond to a very poor CI user performance. The triplet strategy is still showing the best SRTs with no degeneration of the nerve fibers ($b_f = 1$), but looking at the predicted top performance p_{max} , the sequential strategy got always the best results, followed by paired and then triplet. This result suggest that performances evaluated by p_{max} , instead of SRT, may lead to different conclusions.

Figure 40: Psychometric curves in SRT experiments for the three F120 sound coding strategies using only IR as features and good nerve conditions ($b_f = 1$, 9001 fibers). The horizontal black line highlights the 50% threshold. The shadowed area surrounding the curves corresponds to the confidence intervals ($\chi^2 = 3.84$).

Table 3: Results from SRT experiments using all the features.

All the features		Sequential	Paired	Triplet
No Degeneration	SRT [dB]	8.86	7.93	7.54
	p_{max} [%]	91.55	87.49	86.27
	s [%/dB]	0.41	0.43	0.46
Low count of fibers	SRT [dB]	8.58	7.80	7.76
	p_{max} [%]	90.13	87.64	83.28
	s [%/dB]	0.42	0.40	0.51
Fibers fully degenerated	SRT [dB]	11.49	N/A	15.31
	p_{max} [%]	61.65	48.70	55.04
	s [%/dB]	0.53	0.42	0.33

The gap between 100% and p_{max} also diminished considerably and is reduced to less than 20% with healthy fibers ($b_f = 1$) and crossed the 50% threshold in two

out of three experiments with fibers fully degenerated ($b_f = 0$). This means that additional features could help to improve the model performance considerably.

Figure 41 shows that performance of paired and triplet strategies are very similar as their confidence intervals are intercepting each other. Sequential strategy obtained the worse performance. This is also contrary to the obtained results in real CI users by Langner et al. (2017) [5]. Possible reasons may be related to the results obtained using only IR as features, this is further discussed in the next chapter.

Figure 41: Psychometric curves in SRT experiments for the three F120 sound coding strategies using all the features and good nerve conditions ($b_f = 1$, 9001 fibers). The horizontal black line highlights the 50% threshold. The shadowed area surrounding the curves corresponds to the confidence intervals ($\chi^2 = 3.84$).

5.2 Spectral modulation threshold performance

The SMT experiment results are also divided into two groups, the first one using only IR as features and the second one using all the features. Each group has a corresponding table with the SMT, the predicted top performance p_{max} , and the growth rate of the curve s at the inflection point. Tables are organized by nerve

condition and sound coding strategy as well. Best results are considered when SMT is the lowest, p_{max} is the closest to 100%, and the slope s is the steepest, similar to SRT experiments. These values are highlighted with a ***bold-italic*** font, in the respective tables.

For these experiments, the regression functions obtained an R^2 coefficient equal to 0.99 or greater, meaning that the psychometric equation 4.7 is almost a perfect representation of the data. Assuming that CI users performance in SMT experiments resembles also the psychometric function in Figure 13, it is comparable to the proposed model performance.

Table 4 shows the results using only IR as features. All the SMTs correspond to a good performance comparing with obtained CI users data by Litvak et al. (2007) and Langner et al. (2017), as shown in Figures 15 and 16, respectively [5] [26].

Table 4: Results from SMT experiments using only IR as features.

Only IR as features		Sequential	Paired	Triplet
No Degeneration	SMT [dB]	6.88	6.73	6.97
	p_{max} [%]	99.55	99.77	99.95
	s [%/dB]	1.63	1.78	1.35
Low count of fibers	SMT [dB]	6.69	6.56	6.75
	p_{max} [%]	99.68	100	99.73
	s [%/dB]	1.40	1.13	1.59
Fibers fully degenerated	SMT [dB]	7.07	7.74	7.81
	p_{max} [%]	100	100	99.76
	s [%/dB]	1.31	0.80	0.88

Nevertheless, there is not enough difference in the results between the three sound coding strategies, when there is no nerve degeneration ($b_f = 1$), to conclude which one of them is better or worse, as shown in Figure 42. The confidence intervals of the three strategies are intercepting each other at the threshold.

When the nerve fibers are fully degenerated ($b_f = 0$), sequential strategy performs

Figure 42: Psychometric curves in SMT experiments for the three F120 sound coding strategies using only IR as features and good nerve conditions ($b_f = 1$, 9001 fibers). The horizontal black line highlights the 79.40% threshold. The shadowed area surrounding the curves corresponds to the confidence intervals ($\chi^2 = 3.84$).

better than paired and triplet, as shown in Figure 43, but there is almost no difference between paired and triplet performance.

These observations differ from the ones obtained by Langner et al. (2017) in real CI users, where sequential and paired strategies have similar performances while the triplet strategy is clearly worse, as shown in Figure 16 [5]. These observations may suggest that the model is not predicting completely with spectral information but using the overall firing rate of nerve fibers. This discussion is further extended in the next chapter, once all the results are presented.

Table 5 shows the results using all the features. In this case, the performance corresponds to a very good CI user performance according to the obtained data by Litvak et al. (2007) and Langner et al. (2017), as shown in figures 15 and 16, respectively [5] [26].

Introducing new features seems to enhance the spectral information because the

Figure 43: Psychometric curves in SMT experiments for the three F120 sound coding strategies using only IR as features and nerve fully degenerated ($b_f = 0$, 9001 fibers). The horizontal black line highlights the 79.40% threshold. The shadowed area surrounding the curves corresponds to the confidence intervals ($\chi^2 = 3.84$).

Table 5: Results from SMT experiments using all the features.

All the features		Sequential	Paired	Triplet
No Degeneration	SMT [dB]	3.93	3.97	4.13
	p_{max} [%]	100	100	100
	s [%/dB]	2.30	2.25	2.01
Low count of fibers	SMT [dB]	4.03	4.11	4.27
	p_{max} [%]	100	100	99.99
	s [%/dB]	2.58	2.39	2.12
Fibers fully degenerated	SMT [dB]	4.06	4.43	4.81
	p_{max} [%]	100	99.62	99.25
	s [%/dB]	1.92	1.37	1.25

expected order in performance observed in real CI users is also observed in the modeled results (sequential strategy performs better than paired, and paired better

than triplet), but the difference is only significant when the nerve fibers are fully degenerated ($b_f = 0$), as shown in Figure 44. This was expected because, as shown in Figures 33 and 34, the activation functions of the electrodes are less discriminative along the cochlea when the fibers are degenerated, so the spectral resolution is worse.

Figure 44: Psychometric curves in SMT experiments for the three F120 sound coding strategies using all the features and nerve fully degenerated ($b_f = 0$, 9001 fibers). The horizontal black line highlights the 79.40% threshold. The shadowed area surrounding the curves corresponds to the confidence intervals ($\chi^2 = 3.84$).

5.3 Influence of nerve fiber count in overall performance

Looking at Tables 2, 3, 4, and 5, it is evident that the results are not varying significantly when using 9001 or 2251 nerve fibers in the IndiMoCI model. This was expected because the activation function of the electrodes were not changing, but its resolution. To really measure the impact of having less available fibers, the overall firing rate should be normalized in every case adjusting the mapping of the sound coding strategy.

As explained by Fredelake et al., these adjustments require greater amplitude of the biphasic pulses to obtain the same loudness perception when less fibers are available. Stronger biphasic pulses generate a wider electrical spatial spread along the basilar membrane resulting in channel interaction and consequently losing spectral resolution. Fredelake et al. controlled this spatial spread and firing rate with the variable λ [35], but in the proposed model there is not a single parameter to control this features due to the complexity of the electrode-nerve interface. In the discussion of the next chapter, it is proposed some solutions to achieve this firing rate normalization.

Table 6 shows the performance difference in dB when reducing the number of fiber per experiment, where $\Delta SRT = SRT_{NoF=2251} - SRT_{NoF=9001}$ and $\Delta SMT = SMT_{NoF=2251} - SMT_{NoF=9001}$. A negative ΔSRT or ΔSMT value means that the performance improved. Also, biggest performance improvement and detriment are highlighted with *bold-italic* font.

Table 6: SRT and SMT performance difference when reducing the number of fibers.

SRT-SMT performance difference				
Pulse Table	Only IR		All Features	
	ΔSRT	ΔSMT	ΔSRT	ΔSMT
Sequential	<i>0.99 dB</i>	-0.19 dB	-0.28 dB	0.10 dB
Paired	<i>-0.36 dB</i>	-0.17 dB	-0.13 dB	0.14 dB
Triplet	0.04 dB	-0.22 dB	0.22 dB	0.14 dB

Note that the variations are lower than 1 dB, and could be positive or negative, suggesting that they are oscillating inside a confidence interval.

5.4 Influence of nerve fiber degeneration in overall performance

Tables 2 and 3 show that the detriment of performance in speech perception experiments is noticeable when the fibers are fully degenerated ($b_f = 0$). In four out of

six experiments, it was not possible to calculate the SRT because the predicted top performance p_{max} did not reach the 50% threshold, hence the same p_{max} is used as the indicator to study the impact of fiber degeneration, as shown in Table 7, where $\Delta p_{max} = p_{max,b=0} - p_{max,b=1}$.

Table 7: SRT performance detriment when degenerating the fibers.

Δp_{max}		
Pulse Table	Only IR	All Features
Sequential	-41.31%	-29.90%
Paired	-37.63%	-38.79%
Triplet	-40.73%	-31.23%

In all cases, a detriment between 29% and 42% of p_{max} is obtained. This suggest that, in experiments where the psychometric function does not approximate to 100%, the p_{max} should be considered as the indicator of performance instead of the SRT.

In SMT experiments, the nerve degeneration contributed to make the proposed computational model more sensitive to the changes in front-end sound coding strategies, but the total detriment was lower than expected with the biggest difference being 1.01 dB. No matter the nerve conditions, the SMTs corresponded to a good or a very good CI user performance. SMT detriment is shown in Table 8, where the biggest difference is highlighted in a *bold-italic* font for each case of features used.

Table 8: SMT performance difference when degenerating the fibers.

ΔSMT		
Pulse Table	Only IR	All Features
Sequential	0.19 dB	0.13 dB
Paired	<i>1.01 dB</i>	0.46 dB
Triplet	0.84 dB	<i>0.68 dB</i>

As mentioned before, the model could be using information that it is not related to the spectral information but the firing rate. This idea is developed in the next chapter.

Chapter 6

Discussion

This project successfully implemented a computational model that was used to predict SMT and SRT performance. The model is a complex tool, with a large amount of parameters that requires a much more extended study. Nevertheless, it is perfectly capable of performing speech-in-noise recognition and spectral modulation detection experiments with results that are comparable to CI user performance. In this chapter, the principal findings of the project, limitations, and future work are discussed.

6.1 Performance of the proposed model

F120-T sound coding strategy uses simultaneously three current steering channels increasing the interaction between them and causing loss of spectral resolution [5]. In theory, this loss should worsen the performance, but this was not observed in the results. As mentioned in the previous chapter, F120-T strategy performed better than F120-S and F120-P in speech recognition tasks, and the three sound coding strategies performed quite similar in spectral modulation detection.

At first, the results suggest that the model is capable of resolving spectral modulation better than humans, but not the temporal modulations presented in speech. It is known that sound coding strategies that activate simultaneous channels have the

potential to improve the temporal resolution because the pulse rate can be increased [5]. Thus, the gain obtained in temporal resolution, by using the F120-T strategy, appears to be much more significant than the loss in spectral resolution, causing an improvement in performance. The problem is that a zero current phase ("rest") was added between consecutive biphasic pulses in F120-P and F120-T strategies to get the same pulse rate and width as F120-S. This is shown in Figure 12.

Additionally, those "rests" between pulses could allow some auditory nerve fibers to come out of the ARP characteristic of the Joshi et al. (2017) model [19]. Hence, every time a new pair or triplet of channels stimulates simultaneously, there would be more fibers out of the ARP available to code sound. This hypothesis depends directly on the assumption that the model has a very good spectral resolution.

The problem with the previously mentioned approaches is that they cannot explain why the nerve degeneration affects so poorly the SMT performance. A possible explanation is that the HMM is actually learning to discriminate between a spectral rippled noise and a reference noise using the firing rate rather than actual spectral information. The mean firing rate value of each IR channel should be lower in the spectral ripple noise than in the reference noise because the valleys in the spectral shape of the spectral ripple noise diminish the stimulation for a group of fibers. Thus, the model learns to identify if there is a reduction in the firing rate in any IR feature instead of looking at any spectral shape. If this assumption is correct, no matter how different is the activation function or how many channels are used simultaneously, the performance will be always similar. The addition of new features improved the performance because it actually incorporates a feature of overall firing rate and the CICC which introduce spectral shape information.

Figure 45 shows how the overall firing rate of random samples of spectral ripple noise tends to decrease with higher C_t values. The samples were taken from an experiment with a healthy nerve condition using the F120-S sound coding strategy.

The modeled SRT results contradict the empirical data. This result may be explained by the difference in overall firing rate between the sound coding strategies.

Figure 45: Influence of the spectral rippled noise contrast C_t in the overall firing rate. The samples are obtained randomly from a SMT experiment with healthy nerve condition ($b_f = 1$, 9001 fibers) and using the sequential sound coding strategy.

For F120-P and F120-T, the amount of stimulation current is normally reduced to match the loudness perception obtained with F120-S. But, because a general mapping (average across 12 individuals) was used for each sound coding strategy in the experiments, this match in loudness perception is not correctly applied, as shown in Figure 46.

In this case, the reduction of stimulation current applied to F120-P and F120-T strategies was greater than needed, giving them an advantage regarding saturation of the nerve fibers and channel interaction.

6.2 Geometry limitations

The most important limitation of this thesis is that only a generic version of the electrode-nerve interface was used to perform all the experiments. The results cannot

Figure 46: Mismatch in loudness perception of the three F120 sound coding strategies. The y-axis represent the overall firing rate feature obtained by integrating in space and time the spike activity. The same *.wav* file of the sentence *Ulrich gewann zwölf rote Messer* mixed with CCITT noise at 18 dB_{SNR} was used with the strategies.

be generalized to all possible cases of cochlear geometry and these may vary using different mappings and geometries.

The model also lacks a calibration procedure to maintain a "comfortable loudness level" among all sound coding strategies, which is performed in the mapping procedure of CI users. The calibration procedure could be a feedback algorithm from the geometry data (cochlea dimension, electrode positions, number of fibers, and neural health) to the mapping in the sound coding strategy. Both parameters are currently inputs of the model. The drawback is that such feedback algorithm would be different for every sound coding strategy, adding another undesired layer of complexity

to the model.

A possible solution is to control the firing probability of the nerve fibers through the "modeling factor" M_f described in Equation 4.4. If this parameter is individualized for each fiber, the calibration procedure of the model could be simplified and would not depend on the mapping in the sound coding strategy.

This calibration procedure should be activated, deactivated, or manually modified depending on the needs of the experiments.

6.3 Speech reception and spectral modulation threshold relation

Litvak et al. (2007) found a relation between the speech perception and the spectral modulation that is shown in Figure 15 [26]. It is important to say that this relation was found recognizing vowels and consonants using monosyllabic words, so many temporal cues necessary to understand a complete sentence in speech were absent. Nevertheless, a similar relation between SMT and SRT was expected in the experiments, but due to the relatively small variability of the SMT results, as shown in Tables 6 and 8, this relation could not be confirmed by the model.

6.4 New features vs a new back-end

To perform an experiment, the computational model should be limited to only use information from the CI device, the cochlea geometry, the insertion of the electrode array, and the neural health, because these are probably the most important elements explaining performance after cochlear implantation. This means that the computational tool should only focus from whatever happens after the microphone captures the sound wave to the spike activity generation in the peripheral auditory system. Whatever comes next, should completely belong to the back-end processing of the model.

In the proposed computational model, an "adapter" is needed to connect the pe-

ripheral auditory model to its back-end. This adapter is responsible of extracting features from the spike activity as described in Section 4.2. These features are inspired by processes that occur in the central auditory system and adding, or selecting, some of them could improve the performance in SRT and SMT experiments, as shown in Table 9. In this case, from using only IR to using all the features described in Section 4.2, the improvement averaged 1.92 dB_{SNR} in SRT experiments and 2.83 dB_{Ct} in SMT experiments.

Table 9: Improvement obtained by adding features inspired in the central auditory system.

Improvements		Sequential	Paired	Triplet
No Degeneration	<i>SRT</i> [dB]	1.33	2.55	1.46
	<i>SMT</i> [dB]	2.95	2.76	2.84
Low count of fibers	<i>SRT</i> [dB]	2.60	2.32	1.28
	<i>SMT</i> [dB]	2.66	2.45	2.48
Fibers fully degenerated	<i>SRT</i> [dB]	N/A	N/A	N/A
	<i>SMT</i> [dB]	3.01	3.31	3.00

The drawback of including additional features is that, whenever a new feature is added to the adapter, a new layer of complexity is also being added to the system because those features are manipulating the spike activity to feed the back-end, and this should be carefully studied and validated before being implemented.

Additionally, the performance of the computational model could be improved by substituting FADE using another back-end that works directly on the spike activity. The neural networks are part of the current state-of-the-art tools used in many projects related to sound classification and speech recognition that require artificial intelligence [36] [37] [39].

The advantage with neural networks is that the firing probability of its input neurons is already implemented in the peripheral auditory model and many typologies can be tested, such as the spiking neural network (SNN), which can run without demanding to much computational resources. It could meet the requirements of the

computational model, which is limited to recognize only a limited scope of words [39]. The complexity of implementing neural networks relays in designing its internal structure, with layers of neurons, to obtain a performance similar to a CI user. The advantage is that, once the neural structure is completed, it will work as a back-end processing tool directly from the spike activity of the model.

6.5 Reducing the number of fibers

The amount of fibers that has to be modeled is directly proportional to the computational resources that are being used. In Section 5.3, results with 9001 and 2251 fibers were similar, indicating that an optimal number of fibers exist that reduce computational resources without affecting the performance.

6.6 Conclusions

The computational model proposed in this thesis is a first approach to a completely functional computational tool to assist researchers or clinicians dedicated to CIs. It is capable to run speech-in-noise recognition experiments by predicting the SRT and spectral modulation detection experiments by predicting the SMT.

The IndiMoCI cochlear model, in development by the APG, was successfully integrated in the computational model to build a three-dimensional electrode-nerve interface where the geometry of the cochlea and position of the electrodes can be manipulated. The fact that it is possible to reach this level of detail in a simulation tool for CI users represents a novelty and it is the main contribution of this work. Despite the fact that there is still work to do, the model is able to perform experiments similar to CI users.

In SRT experiments, it was shown that the proposed model is sensitive to changes in the front-end sound coding strategies. Also, the results showed a detriment of the performance when the nerve fibers were fully degenerated. In SMT experiments, the model was less sensitive to front-end sound coding strategies and nerve degeneration, but it is proposed the hypothesis that the prediction model is not only using spectral

information, but the overall firing rate as well, to classify between reference noise and spectral ripple noise.

The importance of a calibration mechanism is discussed. Such a mechanism would enhance the robustness of the computational model against variations in the mapping or geometry in the experiments, specially when different front-end sound coding strategies are compared to each other in terms of SRT and SMT.

It is also possible that changing the back-end of the computational model can reduce its complexity. Because the proposed model is already using a GPU to compute the spike activity, a neural network could be the perfect substitute for FADE.

There is a lot of research to follow from this thesis work, and hopefully it will contribute to improve the life of hearing impaired people which is the main motivation of the research community dedicated to this topic.

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Bibliography

- [1] APG. Auditory Prosthetic Group (2019). URL <https://auditoryprostheticgroup.weebly.com>. [Online; accessed 09-May-2019].
- [2] Nogueira, W. & Ashida, G. Development of a Parametric Model of the Electrically Stimulated Auditory Nerve. In Wriggers, P. & Lenarz, T. (eds.) *Biomedical Technology: Modeling, Experiments and Simulation*, 349–362 (Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2018).
- [3] Kollmeier, B., Schädler, M. R., Warzybok, A., Meyer, B. T. & Brand, T. Sentence Recognition Prediction for Hearing-impaired Listeners in Stationary and Fluctuation Noise with FADE. *Trends in Hearing* **20**, 1–17 (2016).
- [4] Schädler, M. R., Warzybok, A., Ewert, S. D. & Kollmeier, B. A simulation framework for auditory discrimination experiments: Revealing the importance of across-frequency processing in speech perception. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America* **139**, 2708–2722 (2016).
- [5] Langner, F., Saoji, A. A., Büchner, A. & Nogueira, W. Adding simultaneous stimulating channels to reduce power consumption in cochlear implants. *Hearing Research* **345**, 96–107 (2017).
- [6] Wikipedia contributors. Outer ear — Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia (2019). URL https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Outer_ear&oldid=892166756. [Online; accessed 18-June-2019].

- [7] Moore, B. C. Coding of sounds in the auditory system and its relevance to signal processing and coding in cochlear implants. *Otology and Neurotology* **24**, 243–254 (2003).
- [8] Mangado López, N. *Cochlear implantation modeling and functional evaluation considering uncertainty and parameter variability*. Phd thesis, Universitat Pompeu Fabra (2018).
- [9] Nogueira, W. *Design and Evaluation of Signal Processing Strategies for Cochlear Implants based on Psychoacoustic Masking and Current Steering*. Phd thesis, Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz Universität Hannover (2008).
- [10] Delano, P. H. & Elgoyhen, A. B. Editorial: Auditory efferent system: New insights from cortex to cochlea. *Frontiers in Systems Neuroscience* **10**, 50 (2016). URL <https://www.frontiersin.org/article/10.3389/fnsys.2016.00050>.
- [11] Heeger, D. Perception lecture notes: Loudness perception and critical bands (2006). URL <http://www.cns.nyu.edu/~david/courses/perception/lecturenotes/loudness/loudness.html>. [Online; accessed 31-May-2019].
- [12] McKay, C. M., Remine, M. D. & McDermott, H. J. Loudness summation for pulsatile electrical stimulation of the cochlea: Effects of rate, electrode separation, level, and mode of stimulation. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America* (2002).
- [13] Ramekers, D. *et al.* Auditory-nerve responses to varied inter-phase gap and phase duration of the electric pulse stimulus as predictors for neuronal degeneration. *JARO - Journal of the Association for Research in Otolaryngology* **15**, 187–202 (2014).
- [14] Stakhovskaya, O., Sridhar, D., Bonham, B. H. & Leake, P. A. Frequency map for the human cochlear spiral ganglion: Implications for cochlear implants. *JARO - Journal of the Association for Research in Otolaryngology* **8**, 220–233 (2007).

- [15] Nadol, J. B. Patterns of neural degeneration in the human cochlea and auditory nerve: Implications for cochlear implantation. *Otolaryngology - Head and Neck Surgery* **117**, 220 – 228 (1997).
- [16] He, S., Teagle, H. F. B. & Buchman, C. A. The electrically evoked compound action potential: From laboratory to clinic. *Frontiers in Neuroscience* **11**, 339 (2017). URL <https://www.frontiersin.org/article/10.3389/fnins.2017.00339>.
- [17] Dejea i Velardo, H. *Simulation study of cochlear implants stimulation protocols and its application to surgical planning*. Bachelor's degree thesis, Universitat Pompeu Fabra (2015).
- [18] Wilson, B. S., Finley, C. C., Lawson, D. T., Wolford, R. D. & Zerbi, M. Design and evaluation of a continuous interleaved sampling (CIS) processing strategy for multichannel cochlear implants. *Journal of rehabilitation research and development* **30**, 110–116 (1993).
- [19] Joshi, S. N., Dau, T. & Epp, B. A Model of Electrically Stimulated Auditory Nerve Fiber Responses with Peripheral and Central Sites of Spike Generation. *JARO - Journal of the Association for Research in Otolaryngology* **18**, 323–342 (2017).
- [20] Wouters, J., McDermott, H. J. & Francart, T. Sound coding in cochlear implants: From electric pulses to hearing. *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine* **32**, 67–80 (2015).
- [21] Zhu, Z., Tang, Q., Zeng, F.-G., Guan, T. & Ye, D. Cochlear Implant Spatial Selectivity with Monopolar, Bipolar and Tripolar Stimulation. *Hearing Research* **283**, 45–58 (2012).
- [22] Nogueira, W., Litvak, L., Edler, B., Ostermann, J. & Büchner, A. Signal processing strategies for cochlear implants using current steering. *Eurasip Journal on Advances in Signal Processing* **2009**, 1–20 (2009).

- [23] Wagener, K., Kuehnel, V. & Kollmeier, B. Entwicklung und evaluation eines satztests für die deutsche sprache i: Design des oldenburger satztests. *Zeitschrift für Audiologie* **38**, 4–15 (1999).
- [24] HörTech. International Matrix Test Reliable speech audiometry in noise (2019). URL https://www.hoertech.de/images/hoertech/pdf/mp/produkte/intma/Broschre_Internationale_Tests_2019_WEB_klein.pdf. [Online; accessed 31-May-2019].
- [25] Jürgens, T., Hohmann, V., Büchner, A. & Nogueira, W. The effects of electrical field spatial spread and some cognitive factors on speech-in-noise performance of individual cochlear implant users - A computer model study. *PLoS ONE* **13**, 1–20 (2018).
- [26] Litvak, L. M., Spahr, A. J., Saoji, A. A. & Fridman, G. Y. Relationship between perception of spectral ripple and speech recognition in cochlear implant and vocoder listeners. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America* **122**, 982–91 (2007).
- [27] Levitt, H. Transformed Up&Down Methods in Psychoacoustics. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America* (1971).
- [28] Wikipedia contributors. Depolarization — Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia (2019). URL <https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Depolarization&oldid=894590346>. [Online; accessed 31-May-2019].
- [29] Rattay, F. The basic mechanism for the electrical stimulation of the nervous system. *Neuroscience* **89**, 335 – 346 (1999).
- [30] Rattay, F., Leao, R. N. & Felix, H. A model of the electrically excited human cochlear neuron. ii. influence of the three-dimensional cochlear structure on neural excitability. *Hearing Research* **153**, 64 – 79 (2001).
- [31] Nogueira, W., Schurzig, D., Büchner, A., Penninger, R. T. & Würfel, W. Validation of a Cochlear Implant Patient-Specific Model of the Voltage Distribution

- in a Clinical Setting. *Frontiers in Bioengineering and Biotechnology* **4**, 1–16 (2016).
- [32] Bruce, L. C. *et al.* A stochastic model of the electrically stimulated auditory nerve: Single-pulse response. *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering* (1999).
- [33] Litvak, L. M., Spahr, A. J. & Emadi, G. Loudness growth observed under partially tripolar stimulation: model and data from cochlear implant listeners. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America* **122**, 967–81 (2007).
- [34] Hamacher, V. *Signalverarbeitungsmodelle des elektrisch stimulierten GehÄrs*. Phd thesis, RWTH Aachen. Wissenschaftsverlag Mainz (2004).
- [35] Fredelake, S. & Hohmann, V. Factors affecting predicted speech intelligibility with cochlear implants in an auditory model for electrical stimulation. *Hearing Research* **287**, 76 – 90 (2012).
- [36] Hannun, A. *et al.* Deep Speech: Scaling up end-to-end speech recognition. Tech. Rep., Baidu Research (2014). URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/1412.5567>. 1412.5567.
- [37] van den Oord, A. *et al.* WaveNet: A Generative Model for Raw Audio. Tech. Rep., Google DeepMind (2016). URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/1609.03499>. 1609.03499.
- [38] CUED. HTK Speech Recognition Toolkit (2016). URL <http://htk.eng.cam.ac.uk>. [Online; accessed 24-April-2019].
- [39] Wu, J., Chua, Y., Zhang, M., Li, H. & Tan, K. C. A spiking neural network framework for robust sound classification. *Frontiers in Neuroscience* **12**, 1–17 (2018).
- [40] Hearing4all. Hearing4all cluster of excellence (2019). URL <https://hearing4all.eu/EN/>. [Online; accessed 09-May-2019].

- [41] Schädler, M. R., Warzybok, A. & Kollmeier, B. Objective Prediction of Hearing Aid Benefit Across Listener Groups Using Machine Learning: Speech Recognition Performance With Binaural Noise-Reduction Algorithms. *Trends in Hearing* **22**, 1–21 (2018).
- [42] Schädler, Marc René and GitHub contributors. fade (2018). URL <https://github.com/m-r-s/fade>. [Online; accessed 15-April-2019].
- [43] Nogueira, W., Harczos, T., Edler, B., Ostermann, J. & Büchner, A. Automatic speech recognition with a cochlear implant front-end. In *International Speech Communication Association - 8th Annual Conference of the International Speech Communication Association, Interspeech 2007* (2007).
- [44] Nogueira, W., Büchner, A., Lenarz, T. & Edler, B. A psychoacoustic "NofM"-type speech coding strategy for cochlear implants. *Eurasip Journal on Applied Signal Processing* **2005**, 3044–3059 (2005).
- [45] Wikipedia contributors. Chi-squared distribution — Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia (2019). URL https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Chi-squared_distribution&oldid=907806184. [Online; accessed 25-July-2019].
- [46] Katti, S. K. & Lancaster, H. O. Chi-Squared Distribution. *Econometrica* (1972).

Appendix A

First Appendix

This appendix contains the 36 figures obtained from the experiments described in Chapter 5.

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Figure 48: Appendix: SRT experiment, F120-P, 9001 fibers, $b_f = 1$, only IR as features.

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